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Functional Disorders of the Bilies Bladder in Pediatric Practice

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***Annotation:** Pathology of the digestive organs today occupies one of the first places in the structure of diseases. Modern problems of pediatric gastroenterology, as mentioned above, are a high level of prevalence, early onset and progression of functional and chronic diseases of the gastrointestinal tract in children, in some cases, the insufficient effectiveness of the treatment and the associated likely adverse consequences determine further study of the mechanisms of development of this pathology, the implementation of treatment and preventive measures at a qualitatively new level, based on the principle of strict individualization when prescribing medications.*

***Key words:** functional disorders, gallbladder and ducts, children.*

Pathology of the digestive organs today occupies one of the first places in the structure of diseases. Functional disorders of the gallbladder and biliary tract (FBD) are one of the most common diseases of the digestive system. In the last decade, there has been a trend towards an increase in prevalence among the child population which accounts for 5-7% [3,6,9].

This can be explained by some medical and social factors, such as unfavorable environmental factors, psycho-emotional overload, early artificial feeding, malformations of the digestive system, family predisposition, intestinal infections, allergic diseases. A close connection has been established between the formation of a child's personality, his socialization in the family, kindergarten, school and the growth of functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT).

It is known that under conditions of acute and chronic psycho-emotional stress, negative emotions form foci of stagnant arousal, which lead to significant autonomic disorders and the formation of organ damage. The role of the genetic factor is quite clearly defined today in the development of functional disorders of the gallbladder, ducts, and sphincter apparatus.

Functional disorder of the gallbladder and bile ducts is a clinical symptom complex caused by a violation of the motor-tonic function of the gallbladder and sphincters of the biliary tract, manifested by impaired outflow of bile and/or increased pressure in the duodenum with the development of

abdominal pain syndrome in the epigastric region, right or left hypochondrium [2, 4, 7]. It is important to know that in most cases, functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract are a secondary disease that has already developed with existing gastrointestinal lesions [1].

From the point of view of modern concepts, the variety of clinical symptoms is associated with the complexity of the anatomical structure of the gallbladder and the sphincter apparatus of the biliary tract, and the peculiarities of their neurohumoral regulation. The gallbladder is an organ controlled by the central and peripheral nervous system that ensures the sequence of physiological processes of bile secretion.

Diagnosis of functional disorders of the gallbladder is based primarily on clinical and anamnestic signs. Clinical syndromes for functional disorders of the gallbladder in children depend on the type of disorders and motor function, and are manifested by three large syndromes: pain, dyspeptic and asthenovegetative.

The pain varies in intensity, it is localized in the epigastric region and right hypochondrium, and radiates to the back. It does not decrease after stool, it decreases insignificantly after taking antacids.

Dyspeptic manifestations are accompanied by bitterness in the mouth, airy belching, a feeling of rapid satiety, heaviness in the epigastrium, nausea and vomiting with bile; intestinal dyspepsia - unstable stool, painless diarrhea alternating with constipation, abdominal discomfort.

Asthenovegetative syndrome is manifested by irritability, increased fatigue, and headache. Such children are characterized by such traits as conscientiousness, punctuality, vulnerability, suspicion, high demands on personal hygiene, and isolation.

Currently, there have been significant changes in approaches to diagnosing FGD in children. Methods such as determination of ejection fraction with cholecystokinin-stimulated cholescintigraphy and endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography are not used. A general blood test, a coprogram, a study of helminths, fecal elastase, a general urinalysis, and urine amylase are recommended. Biochemical blood test - alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, amylase, pancreatic amylase, lipase, gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase, bilirubin, glucose, cholesterol, lipid profile, alkaline phosphatase. Ultrasound of the abdominal organs, echocholecystography, endoscopy.

Treatment of functional disorders of the gallbladder in children consists of normalizing the diet and nature of the diet, using psychotherapeutic methods and using medications with a high level of safety and a wide range of therapeutic effects. Medical nutrition is based on dietary table No. 5. Children's nutrition should be rational, i.e. complete in terms of calories and physiological ingredients.

It is necessary to exclude the consumption of spicy, sour and fried foods. In case of dysfunction with increased sphincter tone, a diet with a normal protein content, maximum limitation of fats (fatty meats, fish), smoked foods, marinades, legumes, confectionery products, processed foods, carbonated drinks, coffee is prescribed.

Recommended products are: cereals (buckwheat, oatmeal, millet, rice, etc.), lean meats, fish, poultry, preference should be given (beef, rabbit, chicken, turkey), low-fat dairy products, vegetables and fruits. But only non-acidic varieties of fruits and berries are allowed. For example, bananas, sweet apples, grapes, watermelon, melon, strawberries, pears. Dried fruits are also recommended.

The main method of correcting functional disorders of the gallbladder and biliary tract is the prescription of medications that restore the passage of bile and eliminate abdominal pain. In this regard, it is advisable to use modern antispasmodics (duspatalin, spasmolgon, buscopan), non-steroidal

anti-inflammatory drugs (ibuprofen, diclofenac, naproxen). To restore transport systems for bile components odeston, ursosan, and chofitol are used.

Choleretic drugs with a different spectrum of action: stimulating bile formation (choleretics, true and hydrocholeretics), stimulating bile secretion (cholekinetics), antispasmodics, anti-inflammatory drugs, hepatoprotectors. While treating it is necessary to know what type of biliary dysfunction. As the basis of basic treatment the drug Urdoxa is used to improve bile rheology, which has litholytic and choleretic effects. Urdoxa is prescribed at a dose of 10 mg/kg body weight and is gradually increased to 15 mg/kg body weight. Take once in the evening, an hour after meals or at night. Duration of treatment ranges from 3 months to 2 years.

Herbal preparations that stimulate the formation of bile include (corn silk, rose hips, mint), and hydrocholeretics (mineral waters “Chartok”, “Essentuki”, “Smirnovskaya”). Additionally to the hypotonic type of gastric disorder, tubage with the above listed mineral waters is used. In this case, it is necessary to ensure the absence of cholelithiasis, severe deformations and kinks of the gallbladder.

Functional disorders of the gallbladder are always accompanied by a syndrome of impaired digestion - malabsorption. To improve the processes of digestion and absorption in the duodenum and correct duodenogastric reflux, enzymes, antacids, intestinal antiseptics, pro and prebiotics are needed. In pediatric practice, modern microgranular forms of enzymes – Creon – are widely used. Creon is prescribed at a dose of 1000 units per 1 kg of body weight, in three doses, after or during meals, in courses of varying durations. Physiotherapeutic methods for the treatment of functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract - physical therapy, balneo-, reflexology, and laser therapy - all of them are used in the form of courses, which, of course, can reduce the risk of relapse of abdominal pain.

Psychotherapeutic influence is important in pediatrics, which consists in eliminating unfavorable psychosocial factors in the family and at school. Any methods of dealing with emotional stress should be studied by psychotherapists.

Modern problems of pediatric gastroenterology, as mentioned above, are a high level of prevalence, early onset and progression of functional and chronic diseases of the gastrointestinal tract in children, in some cases, the insufficient effectiveness of the treatment and the associated likely adverse consequences determine further study of the mechanisms of development of this pathology, the implementation of treatment and preventive measures at a qualitatively new level, based on the principle of strict individualization when prescribing medications.

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